

Interview guide 2023

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Interview guide for SSH scholars about their image data use

[Start recording]

Background information

- What is your educational background?
- What research fields/disciplines do you represent?
- What is your professional title?
- For how long have you been working for this title (in years)?
- For how long have you used images as research data?

Research project (CI)

- Can you tell me about your recent research project where you have utilized digital images as research data?
- Where did the idea for the project come from?
- What are the goals of the project?
- What research methods are used in the project?
- Can you recognize specific phases of the project? Can you describe them? In which of them are you in at the moment?

Working practices (CI)

- Do you work alone or as a part of a research group?

YES =>

- What is your research group alike? How was it put together?
- What is the division of labor? What working practices do you have?
- What are the pros and cons in collaboration?
- What other collaborations do you have?

If the project is multidisciplinary =>

- Does this have an effect on the work?
- What are the pros and cons?

Research data (CI)

- What types of research data do you use in the project?
 - What do you understand by research data?
- What is the role of images as research data in this project?
- What type of images do you use?
- Why did you decided to use images as data? Other data sources?
- Of what the images stand for proof/evidence?
- For what purpose the images are used for? Do you use the images as information or for visualization?
- How many images do you have?
- Do you prefer print/digital? Analog/digital? Does it make any difference?
- How would you describe images as research data? Can you compare them with other datatypes you have used?

Collecting data (CI)

- Who collects the image data in your project?
- From which sources do you search the images? Why from these sources?
- How do you find/search the images?
- What do you consider to be the most useful technique when you were searching for an image?
- What problems do you face when searching the images?
- How do you select the images you are using as research data?
- How do you select those images used for visualization?
- How do you store the images/how can you find them again?
- How do you know your data is “ready”?
- What problems do you have in selecting the images?

Analysing data (CI)

- Do you work with print/digital images? Is there a difference?
- How do you analyse the images? What are you looking from them?
- What is your unit of analysis?
- Do you use specific analysis methods? Why? How is it like?
- Do you use specific software for data analysis?
- Do you use manual or automatic analysis?
- What is the role of image metadata in the analysis? Is there is enough metadata? Can you trust the metadata?
- What “data cleaning” is involved?
- Can you trust the images are accurate? Why or why not? Is this a problem?
- Do you integrate image data with data from other sources?
- What problems do you have in the analysis? What help would you need for the analyses?

Publishing (CI)

- How do you publish your results? Why?
- In what language do you publish? What are your audiences?

- Co-authorship: What is the division of labor in writing?
- How do you present your results from your image data? Textual/Own visualisations?
- What is the role of images in the publications?
- Do you give credit for those originally producing the images? How? Do you use citations?
- Can you publish the images? What does it take to publish them?
- What problems do you have in publishing related with the images?
- Is the image licensing clear or does this require any extra work? Do you need to consult anyone about licensing?
- What open access publishing means to you? Is it important?

Sharing data (CI)

- What happens to your data after publishing?
- Will you archive your data openly? Why, why not?
- Could someone else benefit from your data or your methods? How?
- Where can you archive your data?
- What it takes to open your data for others to use?
- What would you share? Images or data about the images?
- Should data be anonymized? How can this be done? If not, why?
- Are there any ethical questions in collecting, analyzing, publishing, archiving this data?
- Who owns your data? Do you use any licenses for the image data? For reuse etc.?

Ending

- Is there something you would like to add?
- How was the interview in general? Any suggestions for improvement?
- Do you know anyone else I could interview?